

MATRIX CRACKING IN A (0/90)_{2s} GFRP LAMINATE LOADED IN FLEXURE

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SUMMARY: Matrix cracking in a (0/90)_{2s} GFRP laminate loaded in four point bending has been studied experimentally and analytically. Experimental data have been obtained for crack accumulation in the single 90° ply near the tensile face of the laminate as functions of applied bending moment and *in situ* ply strain. The cracks lead to a reduction in the flexural stiffness of the laminate while the partial release of thermal stress associated with crack formation leads to a residual curvature on unloading. Results for crack onset and the residual properties as a function of damage are in reasonable agreement with a closed-form analytical model based on one-dimensional beam theory (with the cracked 90° ply properties degraded in accordance with a shear-lag model) in conjunction with fracture mechanics.

KEYWORDS: Bending, transverse cracks, stiffness, fracture mechanics, cross-ply laminate, residual curvature.

INTRODUCTION

Compared with simple in-plane tensile loading, the development of matrix cracking damage in composite laminates loaded in flexure has received little attention in the literature. Early analytical work concerned with flexural behaviour concentrated on developing beam theory for composite laminates and the application of phenomenological failure criteria. Comparison with experimental data in these studies was limited. More recently, some authors have characterized the behaviour of CFRP rectangular beam elements under flexural loading, e.g. [1,2]. Where comparison is made between the loads at which first ply failure is observed experimentally and the predictions of engineering failure criteria, agreement is generally poor. It is possible that either fracture mechanics or damage mechanics approaches might be better able to predict first ply failure for flexural loading. While there are some closed-form stress transfer analyses in the literature which could be used as the basis for such models, e.g. [3-7], there are few experimental data to enable such approaches to be tested. In the present work experimental data are presented relating to the development of matrix cracking in a (0/90)_{2s} GFRP laminate loaded in flexure. These include crack density as a function of applied moment together with the effect of cracking on residual flexural stiffness and residual curvature. The results are compared with the predictions of a recently developed analytical model. Full details of the model are given elsewhere [5,7].

EXPERIMENTAL

(0/90)_{2s} GFRP laminates were manufactured in house using a frame-winding/wet impregnation route, e.g. [8]. The cured thickness was 4.4 mm. Test coupons 200 mm long and 20 mm wide were cut from the laminates and for some coupons strain gauges were attached to the centre of both faces. Flexural tests were carried out using a four point loading configuration with a central gauge length of 77 mm. The total gauge length was 160 mm. Samples were initially loaded to 0.5 kN (a load below the matrix cracking threshold) so that the initial flexural modulus could be determined within this range. Samples were then subjected to progressively higher load levels which led to multiple matrix cracking in the single 90° ply located towards the tensile face of the beam. Load increments of 0.1 kN were used. After unloading from each load increment the matrix crack density could be determined by direct observation due to the near transparency of the material. The strain gauges enabled the effect of the 90° ply cracking to be assessed in several ways. Firstly, from consideration of the strains on the tensile and compressive surfaces, the location of the neutral axis can be determined. Secondly, the flexural stiffness was measured as a function of crack density. Finally, the partial relaxation of thermal stress associated with matrix crack formation leads to a residual curvature on unloading which can be determined experimentally from the difference between the residual surface strains divided by the laminate thickness. For some specimens the change in curvature was measured directly from the central deflection over a reference gauge length, relative to any initial deflection associated with the laminate not being perfectly symmetric.

The volume fraction of the laminates was 0.52. The relevant principal material property data were $E_1 = 37$ GPa, $E_2 = 9.5$ GPa, $G_{12} = 4$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.28$ and $G_{23} = 3.345$ GPa, using data from [8, 9]. With regard to residual thermal stresses, values of α_1 and α_2 were taken from Mulheron [10] as $6.7 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $29.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and used in conjunction with the value of $(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)\Delta T$ reported by Bassam et al. [11], based on an unsymmetric 0/90 laminate, to determine the effective temperature change experienced by the laminate as a result of cure, $\Delta T = -130^\circ\text{C}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initial Flexural Modulus

The initial measured flexural stiffness of the laminate was 29.3 GPa. A simple one-dimensional model, e.g. [5], gives an expression for the flexural modulus as:

$$E_{flex} = (11E_1 + 5E_2)/16 \quad (1)$$

Substituting the ply properties we find $E_{flex} = 29.1$ GPa, which is in good agreement with the experimental value.

Threshold Cracking Strain

As the applied load, and hence moment, were increased, cracks initiated in the 0.5 mm thick 90° ply towards the tensile face of the laminate. The load at which cracks started to propagate across the laminate width was about 0.8 kN. This corresponds to an *in situ* ply strain in the single 90° ply of just over 0.5 %, or about 0.75 % including the thermal strain. According to the model in ref. [7], the *in situ* ply strain at crack propagation strain is 0.92 % (including thermal strain). This is in reasonable agreement with the experimental value.

Crack Accumulation with Applied Bending Moment

The crack density was determined initially as a function of applied bending moment. Data are shown in Fig. 1. It is apparent that there is a cracking threshold followed by a rapid increase in crack density towards a plateau where the cracks are spaced about two ply thicknesses (1.1 mm).

Figure 1 Crack density as a function of applied bending moment for single 90° ply towards the tensile face of a (0/90)_{2s} laminate loaded in flexure

The Position of the Neutral Axis

In order to compare the crack accumulation data with studies of matrix cracking in laminates loaded in tension, it is necessary to convert the flexure data so that they are in the form of crack density as a function of applied 90° ply strain. A knowledge of the position of the neutral axis is required for this.

Table 1 shows data from two specimens for the tensile face strains (ϵ_T) and compressive face strains (ϵ_C) for an applied load of 0.5 kN for a range of crack densities, D ($D = 1/2s$, where $2s$ is the average crack spacing). The strains are all shown as positive values for ease of interpretation. The values given are changes relative to the values when there was no load applied. There are a number of points that can be drawn from the data. Before the laminate was cracked the top and bottom surface strains (at the load of 0.5 kN) were not equal in magnitude. Typically the difference is between 3 and 5 %. This is most likely associated with the laminate not being perfectly symmetric about the mid-plane with regard to fibre distribution, ply thickness etc. which is consistent with the specimens generally having a small initial curvature after manufacture, typically 0.04 m^{-1} . It is also apparent from the data that the strains (for the same applied load of 0.5 kN) generally increase with increasing crack density; this is consistent with a slight lowering of the flexural stiffness of the laminate as a result of cracking. Given that the top and bottom surface strains differ when the laminate is uncracked, in order to make any inference regarding the movement of the neutral axis as

a result of cracking it is necessary to look at how the difference between the top and bottom surface strains, $(\epsilon_t - \epsilon_c)$, changes with increasing crack density. For both specimens, the quantity $(\epsilon_t - \epsilon_c)$ appears to increase slightly, especially for specimen B. This suggests that the neutral axis moves towards the compressive face of the beam, which is as expected, given that the damage occurs towards the tensile face. The results suggest that the value of $(\epsilon_t - \epsilon_c)$ changes by no more than about $80 \mu\epsilon$, even for the highest crack densities observed. This represents a displacement of the neutral axis of about 0.016 mm . This observation is in agreement approximately with theory [7] which predicts that the neutral axis movement should be very small, about 0.03 mm (towards the compressive face of the beam) for the maximum crack densities here. The displacement is small because of the dominance of the surface O layers in determining the flexural behaviour of the laminate.

Table 1 Tension and compression face strains at a load of 0.5 kN for two specimens over a range of crack densities

Specimen A				Specimen B			
D mm^{-1}	ϵ_t $\mu\epsilon$	ϵ_c $\mu\epsilon$	$(\epsilon_t - \epsilon_c)$ $\mu\epsilon$	D mm^{-1}	ϵ_t $\mu\epsilon$	ϵ_c $\mu\epsilon$	$(\epsilon_t - \epsilon_c)$ $\mu\epsilon$
0	5292	5471	-179	0	5141	4895	246
0.026	5346	5490	-144	0.026	5173	4941	232
0.078	5269	5495	-226	0.208	5125	4895	230
0.312	5400	5572	-172	0.455	5269	5006	263
0.545	5684	5865	-181	0.740	5261	4996	265
0.727	5482	5625	-143	0.922	5399	5113	286
0.857	5385	5537	-152	0.961	5527	5217	310

Crack Accumulation with *in situ* Ply Strain

Since the neutral axis of the beam does not move to any significant extent, simple bending theory can be used to determine the ply crack density as a function of the *in situ* ply strain or, by multiplying the strain by the transverse modulus, the *in situ* ply stress. Fig. 2 shows the 90° ply crack density as a function of the *in situ* ply strain for the specimens in Table 1.

When the data in Fig. 2 are compared with those from another laminate with the same 90° ply thickness loaded in tension, the $(0/90/\pm 45)_s$ laminate investigated by Tong et al. [8], there is good agreement. In particular the threshold cracking stress/strain is similar for the two different loading types, i.e. tension and flexure. Such agreement is expected from a simple stress-based approach to matrix crack onset but is consistent also with fracture mechanics predictions [5-7]. The final crack spacing is also similar, around 1 mm^{-1} .

Fig. 2 Crack density as a function of *in situ* ply strain for single 90° ply towards the tensile face of a $(0/90)_{2s}$ laminate loaded in flexure

Effect of Damage on Residual Properties

Flexural Stiffness

The change in overall flexural stiffness of this $(0/90)_{2s}$ GFRP laminate as a result of cracking was small, difficult to measure and subject to considerable scatter. Data for two samples are shown in Fig. 3. The largest measured stiffness reductions were generally in the range 2 - 4 %. This is less than would be seen for a similar laminate loaded in tension and is a consequence of only 25 % of the available 90° plies cracking under load, as well as the greater role of the 0° plies in determining the flexural (as opposed to tensile) modulus of the laminate. The measured range of values for the flexural stiffness reduction (see Fig. 3) is in reasonable agreement with the predictions of the simple model presented in ref. [7], based on one dimensional beam bending theory. For instance, the model in ref. [7] predicts that at a crack density of 0.8 mm^{-1} the normalised modulus is 0.979, i.e. a reduction of just over 2 %. For comparison, the ply discount value from the same model is 5.1 %.

Fig. 3 Normalised flexural stiffness as a function of transverse ply crack density for matrix cracking of single 90° ply towards the tensile face of a $(0/90)_{2s}$ laminate loaded in flexure

Fig. 4 Residual curvature as a function of transverse ply crack density for matrix cracking of single 90° ply towards the tensile face of a $(0/90)_{2s}$ laminate loaded in flexure

Residual Curvature

The increasing crack density leads to a redistribution of thermal stress in the laminate. In tensile loading of cross-ply laminates, where cracking is symmetric about the mid-plane of the laminate, such redistribution leads to a residual strain [11]. For the laminates loaded in flexure, where the cracking is non-symmetric, a curvature results which increases with increasing crack density. Data for the residual curvature as a function of crack density from four samples are shown in Fig. 4. It appears from these results that the residual curvature is a more sensitive measure of crack accumulation than the flexural stiffness. Also, while there is some scatter from specimen to specimen, the trends are reasonably consistent. Predictions of residual curvature can be calculated as a function of crack density from the analysis in [7]. For instance at a crack density of 0.8 mm^{-1} , the predicted value is 0.037 m^{-1} , while the ply discount value is 0.092 m^{-1} . Again this represents reasonably satisfactory agreement with the data (see Fig. 4) given the simple nature of the analysis.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The development of matrix cracking damage in a laminate subjected to flexure has been examined experimentally and analytically. Data have been obtained for the crack density as a function of applied moment and *in situ* strain in the ply which undergoes matrix cracking. Progressive cracking leads to a reduction in flexural modulus, although this is less than would be seen for tensile loading due to the greater role of the surface 0° plies. The partial relaxation of thermal stresses results in a laminate residual curvature. The results for the onset of matrix cracking, residual flexural stiffness and residual curvature are in reasonable agreement with theoretical predictions.

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